

Importance of Films and Visuals within the Roma Recycle Project

Roma families from across the UK were involved in the Roma: Recycle Reuse Reimagine project, funded by Seasons for Change. March 18th is International Recycling Day and the WEAVE team screened the *Roma Recycle* film, which captures the R:RRR project and includes families involved. The film illustrates the co-creative process of working online during the COVID-19 pandemic.

This capacity building event outlined this project, describing the process of generating inclusive, multilingual materials for schools and families to use on the theme of recycling. Resources and tips were shared followed by a Q&A session. At the event Roma women involved in the making of the book were welcomed: Claudia Tranca from the Roma Project (Coventry), Maria Polodeanu from Reel Master Productions, Martine Smith (Equity Lead from Maindee Primary School, Wales).

Key takeaways:

- Generating inclusive materials is important to the Roma community and also the WEAVE project as it highlights Roma and non-Roma working together to offer alternative discussion points and materials.
- Resistance to stereotypical tropes that circulate mainstream media is necessary and these materials are offering alternative narratives.
- Working with grassroots Roma families, teachers and educators working in the schools systems is a necessary component to ensuring that materials are relevant and reflecting their voices and meeting their needs.
- Academics and Roma community members can collaborate but ethical terms and guidelines need to be established and transparency is key.
- Honouring people's lived experiences and their time was essential to the project and this topic was discussed and seen as important for all involved in the project.
- Artistic creativity and cultural self-assertion of the Roma is possible when engaging young people and this intergenerational aspect is key to engaging multiple generations in a project and honouring that Roma tradition.

Video: <https://youtu.be/VIRy1SmdMpk>